

THE ROLE OF PEDAGOGICAL STAFF IN INCREASING THE INTEREST OF STUDENTS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotation: The content of foreign language teaching cannot be determined without reference to linguistics, which studies languages as specific code systems. People use language (code system) to communicate; communicate through them. The methodology explores the problems associated with foreign language teaching - a code that is comprehensively studied in linguistics. Thus, linguistics describes the norm of language, that is, the set of rules (rules) governing the accepted speech use of language tools, the use of language tools in a person's speech. This article discusses the main goals and the role of pedagogical staff in increasing the interest of students in foreign languages.

Keywords: Foreign language, main purpose, tools, technologies, tasks, rules, communications, methodology, higher education.

It is important to differentiate science, language, and speech for foreign language teaching methods. Modern linguistics understands language as a code of social significance and its rules of operation, which is entrenched in the minds of a group of people. In other words, language is a system of language tools and rules of use required for communication. Speech is understood as the implementation of a language system in certain acts of communication. The concept of "speech" includes both the process itself and the products of this process - speech works. Although language and speech form two sides of a phenomenon, a whole, they act with units specific to each side.

The study of language as a linguistic phenomenon can provide knowledge about the language system, but it does not lead to the use of the system for communication purposes, as evidenced by the practice of teaching English in school. When special attention was paid to the teaching of the language system, its phonetics, grammar, vocabulary, students were unable to use the grammatical rules and words they had mastered in solving the simplest communicative tasks. Teaching ready-made phrases related to specific situations also does not ensure the mastery of the foreign language being studied, because if knowledge of the language leads to the formation of a language system in the learner, he will be able to construct sentences accordingly. can take. the rules specific to this language in relation to grammatical design and the use of words in communication.

When teaching English in school, it is important to follow a sequence from speech to language. This means that the linguistic component, which includes language and speech material, is the first component of the educational content. The choice, sequence, and dosage of formal (linguistic) means of expression are determined by the need for communication. The study of grammar, vocabulary, phonetics is determined by communication, which should lead to a violation of the traditional order of placement of the language system. Student communication is, as a rule, limited to educational registers. The speech statement in the methodology of teaching a foreign language takes the form of a unit of study. This can be an example of a word, phrase, speech sample, or a typical sentence, sample dialogue, or a

monologue statement that is longer than a sentence on a topic or topic. A structural group that combines statements of a different nature (affirmation, denial, exhortation, interrogation) can act as a learning unit. Working with such speech units helps to shape the language system. The training units themselves are real suggestions related to specific situations. They are pronounced with a certain intonation, depending on the communicative intention, in terms of language norms, grammatical and lexical design.

The content of foreign language teaching is influenced by a field of linguistics, such as sociolinguistics, which studies the relationship between language and culture, language and society. As mentioned above, language is one of the main characteristics of a nation, in which it represents the national culture of the speaking people. Therefore, it is necessary to teach a foreign language not only as a new code (method of expression), but also as a source of information about the national culture of the people. Language performs two main functions: communicative and cumulative. Understanding the importance of teaching a foreign language in close connection with national culture is important in strengthening international cooperation. The modern methodology of teaching a foreign language is characterized by a desire to incorporate information about geography, history, social life into the content of teaching - speech material and, in particular, texts for listening and reading. This methodological position has been defined by the term *linguo-cultural*. Linguistic and cultural teaching helps students to master natural, historical realities, spiritual values, and thus helps to achieve the goal of education - the events, facts that students learn in the language they are learning. interpreting settings. It also helps to shape linguistic consciousness. Functional linguistics, which studies the function of language as a means of communication, a means of social interaction, describing the semantic and communicative aspects of language, has had a great influence on the methodology of teaching foreign languages.

In conclusion, the essence of the methodological component of the curriculum is that the teacher not only explains the new material in the learning process and organizes its correct processing, but also offers his students certain algorithms for completing the tasks, giving them teaches basic methods of independent work. Students should also be taught to conduct socio-cultural observations in the process of learning languages and cultures together.

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